

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This March issue of J.UCS contains four interesting papers concerning more theoretical aspects. Hence here is my challenge to all of you: let's also try to get many nice papers in applied areas to do what J.UCS set out to do: cover all areas of computer science!

Today I have two bits of good news. First, the April and May issues will be very substantial special issues edited by Egon Boerger: I am grateful for the great job that he has done as guest editor! Second, the printed volume of J.UCS 1995 has now been on the shelf for some time. You can order it in any bookshop or directly from Springer. The official title of the hard-cover book is J.UCS - The Journal of Universal Computer Science Vol.1, 1995: Annual Print and CD-ROM Archive Edition, ISBN 3-540-62047-8, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg (1996). Editors can order a personal copy of the book at a very much discounted rate as acknowledgement of their help directly from Dr.H.Woessner (woessner@springer.de).

Enough for today,

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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